

A Dermatologist's Approach to Genitourinary Syndrome of Menopause

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Abstract:

Background: Genitourinary syndrome of menopause (GSM) is a debilitating condition caused by hypoestrogenism that presents with vaginal dryness and dyspareunia as well as other genital, sexual, and urinary symptoms. Previously known as atrophic vaginitis, the term GSM is now used.

Objective: To help familiarise dermatologists with diagnosing and managing GSM.

Methods: In total, 218 articles were identified and reviewed by 2 independent authors using PubMed. Articles included were from December 2005 to December 2015. Sixty-seven articles met our inclusion criteria.

Results: GSM is a clinical diagnosis, requiring the presence of symptoms that should be bothersome and not accounted for by another condition. A pH test may help with diagnosis as vaginal pH will be increased from acidic to neutral. The Papanicolaou test is not recommended because of poor clinical correlation. First-line treatment is low-dose local vaginal estrogen therapy, which has proven efficacy and safety. Serum estrogen levels are not significantly affected with the exception of creams containing high-dose conjugated equine estrogens. Other options have yet to be approved for use in Canada but show promise.

Conclusion: GSM is a debilitating and common condition that suffers from barriers to diagnosis and treatment. Current treatments are well tolerated, rewarding, and effective with rapid onset.

Key Words:

Genitourinary syndrome of menopause, atrophic vaginitis, vulvovaginal, lichen sclerosus, menopause, topical estrogen